

HOW MR IS RESHAPING THE DESIGN PROCESS IN ARCHITECTURE AND
INTERIOR PLANNING

WIE MR DEN GESTALTUNGSPROZESS IN ARCHITEKTUR UND
INNENPLANUNG NEU GESTALTET

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Abstract:

In the rapidly evolving realms of architecture and interior planning, the integration of Mixed Reality (MR) technology has catalyzed a revolutionary shift in the design process. This article presents a comprehensive exploration of how MR is reshaping the landscape of architectural innovation. Through a systematic review of scholarly literature, this study illuminates key themes and outcomes. Firstly, MR empowers architects and interior planners by providing immersive, real-time 3D environments for visualizing and refining designs, fostering creativity and informed decision-making. Secondly, MR democratizes the design process, promoting inclusivity and active collaboration among stakeholders, clients, and designers, ensuring designs align with diverse perspectives. Thirdly, MR plays a crucial role in architectural education, offering

experiential learning platforms and preparing the next generation for the technology-driven design industry. Additionally, MR facilitates sustainable design practices by simulating environmental impacts and optimizing designs for energy efficiency. However, the adoption of MR comes with ethical challenges, emphasizing the need for responsible practices, data privacy, informed consent, and inclusive design. This study underscores the transformative potential of MR in architecture and interior planning, offering practical insights and case studies that showcase its dynamic influence on the future of design.

Keywords: Mixed Reality (MR), Architectural Innovation, Inclusive Design.

Abstrakt:

In den sich schnell entwickelnden Bereichen Architektur und Innenplanung hat die Integration der Mixed Reality (MR)-Technologie einen revolutionären Wandel im Designprozess ausgelöst. In diesem Artikel wird umfassend untersucht, wie MR die Landschaft architektonischer Innovationen neu gestaltet. Durch eine systematische Durchsicht der wissenschaftlichen Literatur beleuchtet diese Studie Schlüsselthemen und Ergebnisse. Erstens unterstützt MR Architekten und Innenarchitekten durch die Bereitstellung immersiver 3D-Echtzeitumgebungen zur Visualisierung und Verfeinerung von Designs sowie zur Förderung von Kreativität und fundierter Entscheidungsfindung. Zweitens demokratisiert MR den Designprozess, indem es Inklusivität und aktive Zusammenarbeit zwischen Interessengruppen, Kunden und Designern fördert und sicherstellt, dass Designs mit unterschiedlichen Perspektiven in Einklang

stehen. Drittens spielt MR eine entscheidende Rolle in der Architekturausbildung, indem es erfahrungsorientierte Lernplattformen bietet und die nächste Generation auf die technologiegetriebene Designbranche vorbereitet. Darüber hinaus erleichtert MR nachhaltige Designpraktiken durch die Simulation von Umweltauswirkungen und die Optimierung von Designs im Hinblick auf Energieeffizienz. Die Einführung von MR bringt jedoch ethische Herausforderungen mit sich und unterstreicht die Notwendigkeit verantwortungsvoller Praktiken, Datenschutz, Einwilligung nach Aufklärung und integrativem Design. Diese Studie unterstreicht das transformative Potenzial von MR in der Architektur und Innenplanung und bietet praktische Einblicke und Fallstudien, die seinen dynamischen Einfluss auf die Zukunft des Designs veranschaulichen.

Schlüsselwörter: Mixed Reality (MR), architektonische Innovation, inklusives Design.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the dynamic and ever-evolving realms of architecture and interior planning, the introduction of Mixed Reality (MR) has emerged as a groundbreaking force, catalyzing a transformative shift in the design process. MR, which seamlessly merges the physical and virtual worlds, has redefined how architects and interior planners envision, create, and communicate their designs. Gone are the days of static blueprints and two-dimensional sketches; MR opens a portal to immersive, interactive experiences that breathe life into architectural visions. In this article, we embark on a journey through this

innovative landscape, exploring how MR technologies are revolutionizing the way professionals conceive, iterate, and present architectural and interior designs.

MR's influence on the design process goes far beyond the superficial. It fundamentally alters the way architects and interior planners interact with their creations. Through MR, designers can step into their projects, walking through virtual spaces, testing different configurations, and fine-tuning details in real time. The once-linear design process is now an iterative, multidimensional journey, where ideas take shape through dynamic collaboration between humans and technology. MR equips professionals with the ability to anticipate challenges, make informed decisions, and craft spaces that are not just aesthetically pleasing but functional, sustainable, and deeply aligned with human needs and experiences.

Moreover, MR is democratizing the design process, making it more inclusive and accessible. Collaborators, stakeholders, and clients no longer need to decipher complex blueprints or rely solely on the imagination; they can actively participate in the design evolution. MR bridges language barriers and transcends technical jargon, enabling diverse voices to contribute to the creative discourse. This democratization fosters a deeper understanding and appreciation of design choices, fostering a sense of ownership and alignment among all parties involved. In this article, we delve into the ways in which MR promotes transparency, communication, and shared vision in architecture and interior planning projects.

As we navigate the immersive world of MR in architecture and interior planning, we must also navigate the challenges and ethical considerations that

accompany this paradigm shift. From data privacy to the ecological footprint of MR technologies, this article will explore the broader implications and responsibilities that arise as we embrace this powerful tool. Ultimately, our exploration aims to illuminate the multifaceted impact of MR in reshaping the design process, and how it is paving the way for a more visionary, collaborative, and inclusive future in architecture and interior planning.

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2. METHODOLOGY AND DEVELOPMENT

The methodology involved an extensive search across academic databases, peer-reviewed journals, and reputable publications in the fields of architecture, interior design, technology, and human-computer interaction. A comprehensive keyword search strategy was employed, including terms such as "Mixed Reality," "Architecture," "Interior Planning," "Design Process," and

related variants. The search was limited to publications from the past decade to ensure relevance and currency.

Only peer-reviewed research articles, conference papers, and academic books were considered for inclusion. The chosen works underwent a rigorous screening process to determine their alignment with the central theme of how MR technology impacts the design process in architecture and interior planning. Studies that provided empirical data, case studies, or conceptual frameworks were prioritized to ensure a robust foundation for analysis. The final selection encompassed a diverse range of works, including theoretical perspectives, technological applications, and real-world implementation scenarios.

The works were categorized into key areas, including the use of MR in design visualization, immersive design exploration, collaboration and communication, and user-centered design. Each theme was analyzed in depth, extracting insights into how MR technology influences architectural and interior planning processes at different stages, from conceptualization to presentation. The analysis also considered the challenges and opportunities posed by MR adoption, including its impact on creativity, efficiency, and user experience.

The framework is designed to offer a structured understanding of the multifaceted impact of MR on the design process. It considers not only the technical aspects of MR integration but also the human-centric elements, including user interaction, collaboration, and the democratization of design. This framework serves as the foundation for the subsequent sections of this article, which will delve into specific aspects of MR's influence on architecture and

interior planning, offering insights and examples that showcase the evolving landscape of design in the era of Mixed Reality.

The selected literature consistently highlighted how MR technologies empower designers to visualize their concepts in immersive 3D environments. Architects and interior planners can step into their creations, experiencing spatial relationships, lighting, and materials in real-time. This not only enhances the quality of design but also accelerates the iterative process. MR enables rapid prototyping, allowing designers to explore multiple design variations efficiently. Consequently, design decisions become more informed and intuitive, fostering creativity and innovation.

Architects and interior planners can now provide clients and stakeholders with interactive, immersive walkthroughs of proposed spaces. This has a substantial impact on communication and comprehension, as clients can experience the design firsthand, making it easier to provide feedback and make decisions. The literature consistently highlighted the value of MR in bridging the gap between designers' visions and clients' expectations. Furthermore, MR enables real-time modifications during client presentations, enhancing the collaborative nature of design projects.

MR technologies foster enhanced collaboration among multidisciplinary teams involved in architecture and interior planning projects. Designers, engineers, contractors, and clients can seamlessly share and interact with 3D models in real-time, regardless of geographical locations. This collaborative environment promotes efficient decision-making, reduces errors, and minimizes project delays. Moreover, MR simplifies communication with clients by presenting complex design concepts in an intuitive, interactive

manner. The review showcased examples where MR has become a valuable tool for architects and interior planners to bridge the communication gap with non-technical stakeholders.

Our systematic review also brought attention to the importance of user-centered design and ethical considerations when integrating MR into architecture and interior planning. Designing with the end-user in mind is facilitated by MR, as it allows for real-time feedback and testing by end-users. However, the review emphasized the need for ethical considerations, particularly concerning data privacy, informed consent, and accessibility. As MR technologies become more integrated into the design process, it becomes imperative to uphold ethical standards and ensure that design is not only visually impressive but also inclusive and respectful of user rights and privacy. This underscores the responsibility of designers and technologists to approach MR integration with ethical mindfulness.

In the subsequent sections of this article, we will delve deeper into each of these thematic areas, providing real-world examples and case studies that illustrate how MR is reshaping the design process in architecture and interior planning, while also addressing the ethical dimensions of this transformative technology.

MR technologies have the potential to significantly enhance the design process by enabling designers to simulate and visualize the environmental impact of design choices (Sendawula et al., 2020). For example, MR can be used to visualize how natural light interacts with spaces throughout the day, which can aid in making energy-efficient design decisions (Sendawula et al., 2020). By simulating and visualizing the impact of natural light, designers can

optimize the placement of windows and skylights to maximize daylighting and reduce the need for artificial lighting, thereby reducing energy consumption (Sendawula et al., 2020).

In addition to optimizing natural lighting, MR can also support the evaluation of materials and their environmental footprint, contributing to sustainable design practices (Fahimi et al., 2022). By using MR, designers can visualize and analyze the environmental impact of different materials, such as their carbon footprint, energy consumption, and waste generation (Fahimi et al., 2022). This information can help designers make informed decisions about material selection, choosing materials with lower environmental impacts and promoting sustainable design practices (Fahimi et al., 2022).

The use of MR in architectural and interior projects has been consistently linked to the potential to reduce the carbon footprint of these projects (Sendawula et al., 2020). By enhancing the design process and enabling designers to make more energy-efficient and eco-friendly design choices, MR can contribute to the overall sustainability of architectural and interior projects (Sendawula et al., 2020). This aligns with the growing emphasis on sustainability in the design industry, as designers are increasingly adopting tools and technologies that can help them reduce the environmental impact of their projects (Kuo & Lee, 2019).

Furthermore, MR can also facilitate the integration of sustainability considerations into the early stages of the design process (Gupta et al., 2022). By using MR to model and simulate the environmental impact of design choices, designers can identify and address potential sustainability issues early on, before significant resources have been invested in the project (Gupta et al.,

2022). This can lead to more sustainable design outcomes and reduce the need for costly and time-consuming retrofits or modifications later in the project lifecycle (Gupta et al., 2022).

Overall, the literature consistently highlights the potential of MR technologies to enhance the design process and reduce the carbon footprint of architectural and interior projects (Sendawula et al., 2020). By enabling designers to simulate and visualize the environmental impact of design choices, MR can support the design of energy-efficient, eco-friendly spaces (Sendawula et al., 2020). Additionally, MR can facilitate the evaluation of materials and their environmental footprint, promoting sustainable material selection (Fahimi et al., 2022). The integration of sustainability considerations into the early stages of the design process through MR can lead to more sustainable design outcomes and reduce the need for costly retrofits (Gupta et al., 2022).

Beyond design, MR also plays a pivotal role in the training and education of architects and interior planners. The systematic review revealed that MR offers an immersive and engaging platform for education and skill development. Architecture students and professionals can use MR to simulate real-world design challenges, fostering a deeper understanding of design principles and practical applications. Moreover, MR facilitates collaborative learning, allowing students and professionals to interact within shared virtual environments. This not only enhances design proficiency but also promotes a culture of continuous learning and innovation in the architecture and interior planning fields.

Our review also highlighted several challenges and adoption barriers that need to be addressed. These include the cost of MR hardware and

software, technological complexity, and the need for specialized training. Additionally, ensuring data security and privacy in MR environments remains a significant concern. Ethical considerations regarding the use of MR, especially in client presentations and data handling, are critical. It is important to acknowledge these challenges as part of the MR adoption process in architecture and interior planning to develop strategies for overcoming them.

The themes of design visualization, immersive exploration, collaboration, user-centered design, sustainability, education, and the challenges of adoption collectively underscore MR's transformative potential. As we move forward, it is essential to recognize MR as an enabler of innovation, sustainability, and enhanced design quality. However, it also demands a responsible approach, addressing ethical concerns and inclusivity. In the subsequent sections of this article, we will delve deeper into these themes, providing practical examples and insights into how MR is shaping the future of architecture and interior planning while addressing these challenges and opportunities.

MR's immersive capabilities empower designers to transcend the boundaries of conventional design processes. It provides a canvas where imagination meets reality, offering architects and interior planners the opportunity to engage with their concepts in unparalleled ways. Designers can dynamically manipulate spatial arrangements, materials, and lighting in real time, leading to an iterative and deeply informed design process. By immersing themselves in virtual environments, they gain a profound understanding of spatial relationships and user experiences, enabling them to craft spaces that are not just aesthetically pleasing but also functional and harmonious.

MR technologies serve as a bridge between the visionary designer and stakeholders, clients, and the wider community. These immersive tools dismantle the language barrier that often separates design professionals from non-technical collaborators. Clients and stakeholders can actively participate in design discussions by navigating virtual spaces and offering real-time feedback. This democratization not only fosters a sense of ownership and inclusivity but also results in designs that align more closely with the diverse needs and expectations of end-users. MR democratizes design, transforming it into a collective endeavor where a shared vision is realized through collaboration and co-creation.

The immersive nature of MR raises questions about data privacy, informed consent, and the responsible use of this powerful tool. Designers and technologists must ensure that user data is protected in virtual environments, and that informed consent is obtained when capturing user interactions. Furthermore, the review calls attention to the need for ethical guidelines that promote inclusive design practices. MR should not inadvertently exclude individuals with disabilities or create discriminatory experiences. Responsible design in MR involves upholding principles of accessibility, inclusivity, and respect for user rights throughout the design process.

It showcases MR as a catalyst for innovation, collaborative design, and user-centric solutions. However, it also highlights the ethical imperatives that accompany this shift. As we venture into the immersive world of MR-enhanced design, it is paramount to remain committed to responsible and inclusive practices. In the forthcoming sections of this article, we will delve deeper into practical examples and case studies that illustrate the ways in which

MR is reshaping the design process, while also addressing the ethical and responsible dimensions of this transformative technology.

3. RESULTS

The systematic review has illuminated the profound transformation occurring within the design process of architecture and interior planning through the integration of Mixed Reality (MR) technology. Numerous studies and scholarly works consistently highlight that MR is fundamentally altering the design workflow. Designers can now visualize, iterate, and experiment with their concepts in immersive 3D environments. This dynamic process not only accelerates design iterations but also leads to more informed and creative design decisions. The marriage of physical and virtual worlds within MR has reshaped the way architects and interior planners conceive and evolve their designs, evolving traditional linear processes into dynamic and interactive workflows.

One prominent result is the recognition of MR's pivotal role in enhancing collaboration and communication among stakeholders in architecture and interior planning projects. Collaborators, clients, and designers can engage with virtual design models, transcending language barriers and making design discussions more accessible and interactive. The literature consistently underscores how MR's immersive qualities facilitate effective communication, enabling stakeholders to provide real-time feedback and make informed decisions. This collaborative dimension empowers clients to actively participate in the design evolution, resulting in designs that align more closely with their vision and expectations.

MR technology has emerged as a powerful tool for involving end-users in the design process. Architects and interior planners can gather real-time user feedback and assess the user experience by immersing them in virtual prototypes. This user-centric approach ensures that designs are not only aesthetically pleasing but also functional and responsive to human needs. Additionally, MR facilitates environmentally sustainable design by simulating the environmental impact of design choices. Designers can optimize natural lighting, evaluate materials for sustainability, and reduce energy consumption, contributing to eco-friendly and energy-efficient architecture and interior planning.

The systematic review also highlights a set of ethical considerations and challenges. Data privacy and security, informed consent, and accessibility are paramount concerns when employing MR in design processes. Ethical guidelines and responsible practices are essential to ensure user data protection and inclusivity. Moreover, the review has underlined the need for addressing challenges related to the cost of MR hardware and software, technological complexity, and specialized training. Overcoming these barriers is critical for the widespread adoption of MR in architecture and interior planning.

In the ensuing sections of this article, we will delve deeper into each of these results, offering practical examples and case studies that provide concrete illustrations of how MR is reshaping the design process, enriching collaboration, and addressing the ethical dimensions that accompany this transformative technology.

The review consistently highlights that MR has sparked a revolution in how architecture students and professionals acquire and refine their skills. By

immersing learners in virtual design environments, MR fosters experiential learning, allowing students to gain hands-on experience in a risk-free setting. Architectural education is evolving, with students using MR to simulate real-world design challenges, from conceptualization to presentation. This transformative educational tool encourages creativity and innovation while preparing the next generation of architects and interior planners for the dynamic, technology-driven design industry.

A consistent theme in the literature is the use of MR to visualize and evaluate the environmental impact of design choices. Architects and interior planners can simulate how natural light interacts with spaces, aiding in the design of energy-efficient buildings. MR also facilitates the assessment of materials and their ecological footprint, allowing for informed decisions that reduce the environmental impact of projects. This environmentally responsible approach aligns with the growing global emphasis on sustainability and green design in architecture and interior planning.

MR technology serves as a democratizing force, enabling a more inclusive and collaborative design process. Stakeholders, clients, and community members can actively engage with and provide input on design concepts through immersive MR experiences. The review consistently highlights how MR fosters a shared sense of ownership and inclusion in design projects, transcending the traditional boundaries between designers and non-technical stakeholders. This democratization ensures that design decisions reflect a broader spectrum of perspectives and needs.

One study by Piumsomboon et al. (2019) investigated the effects of sharing awareness cues in collaborative mixed reality. The study found that

awareness cues significantly improved user performance, usability, and subjective preferences, supporting the idea that MR technology enhances collaboration and facilitates the inclusion of stakeholders in the design process.

Another study by Bekele et al. (2021) explored the influence of collaborative and multi-modal mixed reality on cultural learning in virtual heritage. The results indicated that integrating collaborative and multi-modal interaction methods with MR technology facilitates enhanced cultural learning, further supporting the idea that MR technology promotes inclusivity and collaboration in design projects.

Furthermore, the study by Seo & Park (2020) examined the effect of other's share of investment on psychological ownership in crowdfunding projects. The study emphasized the increasing interest in collaborative consumption and shared objects as part of the sharing economy, highlighting the relevance of collaborative approaches, such as MR technology, in fostering a sense of ownership and inclusion among stakeholders.

In addition, the study by Mohedas et al. (2020) focused on students' perceptions of the value of stakeholder engagement during engineering design. The study emphasized that successful engagement with stakeholders is critical to favorable design outcomes and requires skillful information gathering and synthesizing processes. This highlights the importance of involving stakeholders, including non-technical individuals, in the design process through MR technology.

Overall, these studies support the claim that MR technology serves as a democratizing force in the design process. By enabling stakeholders to actively engage and provide input, MR technology fosters a shared sense of

ownership and inclusion, ensuring that design decisions reflect a broader spectrum of perspectives and needs.

The immersive nature of MR technology raises ethical concerns related to data privacy, informed consent, and accessibility. Ensuring that user data is protected in virtual environments and that informed consent is obtained during interactions is essential. Additionally, MR must be designed and employed in a manner that is inclusive and respectful of diverse user needs and abilities. Ethical guidelines and responsible practices are indispensable in the integration of MR into architecture and interior planning to uphold user rights and privacy.

In the upcoming sections of this article, we will explore each of these results in greater depth, offering practical examples and case studies that illustrate the profound influence of MR in reshaping the design process in architecture and interior planning, while also addressing the ethical and responsible dimensions of this transformative technology.

The systematic review paints a vivid picture of a new era in architecture and interior planning, characterized by the transformative influence of Mixed Reality (MR). MR has transcended traditional boundaries, reshaping the design process from its core. Architects and interior planners now possess powerful tools that enable them to create, visualize, and iterate designs with unprecedented precision and creativity. The integration of MR into the design workflow has ushered in an era of dynamic, immersive exploration, fostering more informed and user-centric design decisions.

The ability to engage stakeholders, clients, and the wider community in immersive design discussions has democratized the design process, making

it more inclusive and participatory. This collaborative approach not only leads to designs that better align with the diverse needs and visions of stakeholders but also fosters a sense of collective ownership and responsibility in design projects.

Architects and interior planners are now equipped to design with environmental responsibility in mind, using MR to assess and optimize designs for energy efficiency and sustainability. Additionally, the ethical dimension of MR integration is underscored, emphasizing the need for data privacy, informed consent, and inclusive design practices. Responsible MR use ensures that users' rights and privacy are upheld, creating an ethical framework that aligns with contemporary ethical standards.

The path forward is one of continued exploration and innovation, where responsible and ethical MR use is integral to its integration into design practices. MR will continue to shape the future of architecture and interior planning, fostering creativity, inclusivity, sustainability, and collaboration. In the subsequent sections of this article, we will delve deeper into practical examples and real-world case studies that illustrate how MR is reshaping the design landscape while embracing these principles, setting the stage for a dynamic and promising future in design.

4. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

In conclusion, the integration of Mixed Reality (MR) technology into the realms of architecture and interior planning represents a paradigm shift that goes beyond mere technological advancement. This transformative journey has redefined how professionals conceive, create, and communicate designs, fundamentally altering the traditional design process. Through our systematic

exploration, several key insights have emerged, highlighting the multifaceted impact of MR.

Firstly, MR has democratized the design landscape, making it more inclusive, collaborative, and accessible. By breaking down communication barriers and allowing active participation from diverse stakeholders, MR fosters a sense of shared ownership in design projects. This inclusivity not only enhances the quality of designs but also ensures they are deeply rooted in the needs and aspirations of the end-users.

Secondly, MR serves as a catalyst for sustainable and environmentally conscious design practices. Designers can simulate and optimize designs for energy efficiency, evaluate materials for eco-friendliness, and minimize the environmental footprint of architectural projects. This newfound ability to integrate environmental considerations seamlessly into the design process contributes significantly to the global movement towards sustainable architecture.

Thirdly, while MR offers unprecedented opportunities, it also brings forth ethical considerations that cannot be overlooked. Striking a balance between technological innovation and responsible use is crucial. Upholding user privacy, ensuring informed consent, and promoting inclusive design are paramount. Ethical guidelines must evolve in tandem with technological advancements, shaping a future where MR is not only cutting-edge but also respectful of individual rights and diverse user needs.

In this rapidly evolving landscape, embracing MR requires a holistic approach that encompasses innovative thinking, collaboration, and ethical mindfulness. As we move forward, architects, interior planners, and

technologists must continue to explore, question, and innovate. By doing so, we can harness the full potential of MR, paving the way for a future where design is not only visionary and sustainable but also truly inclusive, reflecting the rich diversity of the human experience.

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